

The quest for solidarity and reconciliation in Madagascar

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Contemporary Malagasy society seems to be haunted by a number of related ideas: the importance of a special, Malagasy solidarity and an urgent need to create such solidarity for use within the political and social process, as well as the necessity for reconciliation, national unity, and a refounding of the nation. These thoughts enter the social and political agenda in different forms, sometimes explicitly, sometimes silently and indirectly. Occasionally, in moments of highest tension, they make their way into the core of the nation state and its political process, including collaboration with manifold international partners and political mediators. While there is obviously an urgent need for many Malagasy to express these ideas, at the same time they face difficulties in explaining their meaning, their urgency, and how they can be adapted to existing structures and dynamics of the nation state.

One might argue that the more than obvious difficulties of present-day Madagascar are enough to make the quest for solidarity, or refoundation, only too comprehensible. The population has experienced a staggering and unprecedented decline in its economy over more than four decades that is unique, even on a global level, while the population has nearly quadrupled from around 6.5 to nearly 25 million. Economic liberalism since the 1990s has allowed a small fraction of the population access to hitherto unknown prosperity, creating an enormous gap between the many poor and few rich. Mounting insecurity is another important element of public concern. The most important problem, though, is the tremendous difficulty of establishing reliable and continuous collaboration within the population, and between state actors and the population in particular. A common cause, well-anchored and able to create a long-term positive trend for the sake of the entire society is simply not discernable, beyond a strong, abstract patriotism and political proclamations of future national prosperity. Some go as

far as calling the present situation a silent “genocide.” Hence, the call for solidarity, unity, and reconciliation.

In the following paragraphs I will argue, however, that this kind of reasoning is not enough to explain the appeal of the idea of solidarity and the longing for a radical rupture in Madagascar. A first, superficial glance at the socio-political evolution that began at the end of 19th century—with its switch first from a Madagascar divided into many independent territories and identities, to French colonial government in 1896, and later, in 1960, to independence—reveals elements of incongruence already apparent. Why, for example, should modern Madagascar follow the example of countries profoundly shaped by grave conflicts in the recent past, like South Africa or Rwanda; and why, therefore, would Madagascar need the “Council of National Reconciliation” created in 2013? Has the island not lived out the 20th century through a silent, barely noticed turn away from a warring past to a society based on norms of non-violence and consent, a turn that has fortunately helped it to avoid the circle of violence and counter-violence endemic in many other post-colonial states? Why, then, should this peaceful country with such an outstanding and successful record of violence prevention, successfully established in the absence of modern methods of peace-building, now suddenly feel drawn to refoundation and an urgent need to create solidarity?

To better understand the current situation, I propose, it is necessary first to recall the cultural history of an often-emphasized Malagasy term and practice of solidarity called *fihavánana*, which developed in the 20th century into a major symbol of both the Malagasy past and modern Malagasy identity. Further, it is necessary to analyze the more recent trend towards the creation of state-embedded institutions of solidarity, grounded not only in a re-discovery of Malagasy values but also located within the global dynamics of formalization, institutionalization, and heritagization, and by the necessity of some kind of subversive adaptation of local ideas of

solidarity by Malagasy actors to the external world, so as to remain compatible and recognizable partners on the international stage and within the politics of global peace-making.

[Drop-cap 1] In an interview published in September 4, 2018 in the daily newspaper *Midi Madagasikara*, Orlando Robimanana, a candidate in the forthcoming presidential elections of 2018, articulated what he sees as one of the fundamental problems facing Malagasy society: “Malagasy cultural values are in decline. Solidarity, mutual respect, the fihavanana, the feeling of belongingness, national ambition. Right now, egoism is present in all areas.” Only several days before, in a socio-political analysis published as an “open letter to the actors of political life,” a member of the Malagasy diaspora claimed the urgent necessity of “brotherly collaboration” before presenting “the fihavanana (concord)” as a central value to be instituted at the level of local communities. Furthermore, Zaza Ramandimbarison, a former vice-prime minister, suggested, in a recently published manifestation of his political vision entitled “Madagascar, a nation to be constructed,” as the first of ten values “the communal aim to reconstruct Madagascar as a unified nation, [...], inspired by the ‘FIHAVANANA’ [...].”

These and many other similar statements bear witness to a deep concern of Malagasy actors and citizens with the problem of unity, mutual assistance, and solidarity, often with direct reference to the Malagasy term ‘*fihavánana*,’ regularly left untranslated in their French written assertions. This latter particularity tells us that the term is already regarded as possessing a unique Malagasy meaning that has no compelling translation. This meaning, one might suppose, is presumably located in the past and understood to be an expression of authentic Malagasy tradition and identity; as is often the case, the negotiation of a problematic present urges social actors typically to search in the closer or far away past of that culture for an element that can serve as basis for healing the disorder. And in fact, this is precisely the case, as the Malagasy constitution from 1992 confirms explicitly. In its preamble it is inscribed that “The

sovereign Malagasy people” are “profoundly attached to their cultural and spiritual values, notably to the ‘*fihavanana*’ (enlarged kinship), guarantee of national unity.”

The word *fihavánana*, to first elaborate on some elements of its meaning, is based on the expression “*hávana*,” which means “kinship;” a literal translation would of *fihavánana* would be, consequently, something like “to make kinship.” The central idea of *fihavánana* is to establish some kind of reciprocal relationship between individuals by referring to their common biological affiliation, or, one could also say, the assumed weight of their shared origin of life (*aina*). Any one person’s (or group’s) *fihavánana* would naturally encompass close and remote family, the close neighborhood, or even the whole community of a village. While the idea of a community based on the *fihavánana* of an average Malagasy would not extend much further, the concept nevertheless implies a universal aspect and is potentially all-inclusive. It is possible to extend the *fihavánana*-relationship to everybody seen as possessing a meaningful link to an individual or group of people, and it is this capacity that certainly motivated its use for uniting people during the construction of former kingdoms, or later during the process of Malagasy nation-building.

In fact, while it is obvious that some ideas and practices of group or clan solidarity have existed throughout the cultural history of Madagascar, it is very difficult to know about them more precisely, including the terms formerly used. While the term *fihavánana* appears for the first time in 19th century dictionaries compiled by English missionaries, it did not attract any special attention during this period. The ascent towards its remarkable position today started only in the late 1930s when Malagasy catholic authors tried, in the context of French colonialism and the felt rupture of modernity, to describe aspects of a unique Malagasy identity including reference to the concept of *fihavánana*—also used to express the notion of Christian love—in order to establish greater independence from the colonial regime. The breakthrough to today’s prominence arrived in the early 1970s when Malagasy politics turned towards decolonization,

pushing the quest for Malagasy identity to the forefront of public concern. The idea of *fihavánana* as a pillar of the traditional value and essence of Malagasy life became mainstream during this decade, promoted explicitly through, among other channels, school education. It has thus become one of the main terms and conceptual instruments used to re-evaluate what are seen as truly Malagasy, pre-colonial or traditional values and the concept of life, as opposed not only to those of France, but also to what was experienced as a major cultural rupture as a result of the arrival of European values or, more generally, modernity.

In consequence, today a statement on the importance of *fihavánana*, or solidarity, or enlarged kinships, is not just a reference to what is perceived to be an important cultural value in the present, but also implies a reference to the “true” Malagasy, post-colonial past—seen as a time of harmony and consensual understanding in contrast to more modern times of conflict and egoism. It is, ultimately, a conservative term, contrasting traditional Madagascar with the new period of rupture with the authentic. It entails, therefore, silent opposition to the modern state and life. Hence, repeated calls for solidarity, the making of solidarity, or the refounding of the state refer to the idea that a re-integration of old values such as the *fihavánana* might heal the problems of the modern state.

The fading of a violent Malagasy past against an image of solidarity and mutual understanding might at first seem a problematic contradiction. But the cultural logic, as opposed to the historical facts, seems to be this: the need to establish a counterweight to the French-European impact and construct a meaningful nation naturally necessitated looking back to the past. Because it was the idea of *fihavánana* as central, normative, and regulatory in enforcing solidarity consent within groups that was most present in the individual memory, it “naturally” became a central element of Malagasy cultural heritage.

[Drop-cap 2] The insistence on ideas of solidarity and re-foundation is not only a very widespread notion within contemporary Malagasy society, reflecting a general malaise vis-à-vis the ongoing socio-political process, but in the last 35 or so years it has also entered the state and the process of nation-building in more concrete ways. An ambivalent process of formalization, officialization, and institutionalization is well underway, testifying on the one hand to the importance of what is seen by many local actors as truly Malagasy values, but also paying tribute to global processes and conditions of administration and negotiation, on the other.

At the beginning of the 1990s, when the rupture with the long-standing socialist regime of Didier Ratsiraka was finally successfully enforced by the opposition, a new, third, constitution was adopted under elected president Albert Zafy, a fervent supporter of ideas such as the *fihavánana* and reconciliation. In the re-formulated preamble of the 1992 constitution was inscribed for the first time the above-cited passus including mention of “‘fihavanana’ (enlarged kinship)” as the “guarantee of national unity.” The reference to Malagasy solidarity was retained during subsequent changes of government and amendments to the constitution.

In the newly adopted 4th constitution of 2010, however, this formulation was expanded and specified. Now, one encounters an initial phrase stating that the Malagasy people are “determined to promote and develop their heritage of a society living in harmony, and respectful to the alterity, and to the richness, and dynamics of its cultural and spiritual values, through the ‘fanahy maha-olona.’” This untranslated Malagasy expression means something like the “common wisdom of the people.” The next paragraph develops this idea in a very interesting way. The preamble now states “the need for Malagasy society to rediscover its originality, its authenticity and its Malagasiness,” which says nothing more than that it is surprisingly a prime task of today’s population to recognize, and re-construct, a presumably lost cultural heritage. The phrase goes further, urging the population to recognize the importance of taking part in the

“modernity of the millennial” on the one hand, while on the other “conserving its values and fundamental traditional principles, including “ny fitiavana [love], ny fihavanana, ny fifanajàna [respect], ny fitandroana ny aina [responsibility].”

Such an important expansion of the former short reference to the *fihavánana* was the result of a long process of negotiation during the political transitional period after 2009, including various methods of popular consultation, e.g. by a national conference attended by local representatives for each of the 119 districts in 2010. At this event, the importance of Malagasy cultural values and the necessity of integrating them into the nation state was very clearly expressed by local actors who radically re-formulated the constitution, including adding a totally new chapter on *fihavánana*. Their proposals, however, were eventually largely discarded, apart from the altered preamble cited above and the addition of a new, important article.

Article 168, the final one of the reviewed constitutions, stipulates the creation of a new institution to be called “Filankevitra Fampihavanana Malagasy” (FFM) or (in French) “Conseil du Fampihavanana Malagasy” (CFM, i.e. Council of Fampihavanana Malagasy, or, literally, “Council of Making Malagasy Solidarity”). Beyond expanding the declarations in the preamble, then, the year 2010 also marked a truly new chapter in the modern idea of *fihavánana*: for the first time, the urgent wish for the practice of “Malagasy solidarity” made its entrance into the institutional structures of the “new”, i.e. post-colonial, modern state system, and this at a very prominent position; as a constitutional institution, ranking on equal terms with the parliament, the senate, or the High Constitutional Court.

The assertion made in the 4th constitution was finally adopted into law in 2012 upon the creation, mission, and organization of the new institution. In 2013, the elected council with 44 members became functional under its first president, former general Sylvain Rabotoarisoa, with

a mandate for three years and a headquarters in the center of Antananarivo. This first period passed largely without major incident and further public interest, mostly because of this calm period in national politics. Things changed, however, with the second mandate which began in 2017. At this time, the CFM (from this time this abbreviation was commonly used) had been re-organized, now comprising 33 members (with 11 selected by the Malagasy President), and with newly-elected Alphonse Maka as head of the council. In the first month of 2018, a fierce dispute concerning the reformed electoral laws eventually developed into a political crisis, which proved to be the first real test for the CFM.

Before considering this “test” in detail, it is perhaps necessary to explain more precisely the origins and conditions of the outlined process of the institutionalization of the *fihavánana*-idea. While the engine or driving force behind this process are clearly Malagasy actors at various levels of society and their wish to establish links to the idea of *fihavánana*, the process underway is probably, I would argue, much more complex and dependent on conditions extending far beyond the context of the island. First, the orientation towards, and the valorization or, ultimately, the construction, of meaningful “tradition,” “authenticity,” and cultural heritage is a broad and rising global cultural stream that is recognizable on all continents, the UNESCO global heritage program being its best-known institutional structure. Second, the process of valorization of the *fihavánana* enters, somehow both naturally and enforced, the global tendency towards formalization, bureaucratization, and institutionalization, thereby creating a new kind of cultural practice that is very different from the presumed “old” or “traditional” one.

Third, and most importantly, the creation of an institution like the CFM should be understood as part of a delicate interpretation by Malagasy actors of the ideas, constraints, and wishes of their international partners from which, one has to add, a main part of the state budget derives and hence on which the actual subsistence of the country depends. One guiding principle of

Malagasy politics would be, one has to conclude, to comply as much as possible with what one presumes would be approved by these partners—a perspective that engenders important open and even more subtle responses or “mirror” effects. The setup of the FFM/CFM between 2010 and 2013 was, it is suggested, not only the simple outcome of the simple desire to establish an institution of *fihavánana* by the Malagasy actors and to introduce original Malagasy values into the very difficult process of political negotiations of the political crisis since 2009; it also responded, I believe, positively to the knowledge and recognition of international negotiators of the institution of reconciliation in various African countries, and to their attitude assumed as by Malagasy actors, even if the history of political conflict in Madagascar differed substantially. Further, the focus on “traditional” concepts or values is internationally a generally well-accepted and valorized perspective, as long as it does not interfere with higher political aims. By claiming the importance of concepts like *fihavánana*, more than introducing a new method of political conflict solution, Malagasy actors would have shown their cultural responsibility and sensitivity – and would have suggested to their international partners to concede to this idea. Finally, and most importantly, I would argue that global recognition of appeasement structures of all kinds as a major, acknowledged target, made the construction of a new institution on “the making Malagasy solidarity” a very interesting option for Malagasy political actors. The creation of an easily recognizable “anchor institution” for reconciliation would, as they were certainly well aware, mean establishing a main contact address for all representatives of the international community sent regularly to Madagascar for consultation—and would prove the readiness of the Malagasy side to resolve possible conflicts, actively promote peace-making, and be an integral part of the international community. The idea of re-valorizing old Malagasy values of consent here, in a way, matches perfectly the new global norm of conflict-prevention, negotiation, peacekeeping, and pacification.

[Drop-cap 3] The creation of the CFM institution was made possible by a double condition, it was argued: by the necessity felt by political and social actors to re-discover and re-integrate an imagined idea of Malagasy consent within the state, and by a global context favoring institutionalized structures of consent and peace-building. The question of an effective, positive impact on the shaping of the political process, however, was less to the fore. How to acquire, in particular, the political or moral authority necessary for effective social or political mediation? Recent political events revealed more precisely the difficult position characteristic of the present CFM in the ongoing socio-political process.

In April 2018, the adoption of new electoral laws for the forthcoming presidential election were fiercely disputed between the government and the opposition, and a clash between opposition and security forces on April 21st led to two persons being killed and several more being injured. During the subsequent political negotiations, Alphonse Maka, president of the CFM, viewed suspiciously by part of the media and the opposition as possibly being dependent on the Republic's president, assumed a very active position as institutional interlocutor between the government, the opposition, and international partners. The solution to the crisis, however, ultimately depended on the juridical decision of the High Constitutional Court (HCC), appealed to by the opposition. Following the sentence of the HCC on May 25th, the President was obliged to appoint a new, oppositional government within ten days.

During this most tension-filled period, the CFM invited all Malagasy political actors, including many minor or barely known political activists, to a suddenly called high-ranking political summit. However, the most influential politicians did not attend. At the event, Alphonse Maka proposed the idea of seeking a political route, including a postponement of the elections and the organization of new institutions of reconciliation. As the "summit" coincided with the last days of the deadline set by the HCC for announcing a new, opposition prime-minister, the rather brusque action taken by the CFM allowed for ambiguous interpretations and made an

appropriate response or reaction rather difficult for central political actors. The envisaged signing of a political agreement by participants eventually failed because of misunderstandings about the document, among other reasons. Tensions were so high that some participants were driven to open dispute and physical struggle. These events were immediately shared on social media, making the summit an obvious failure in public opinion.

These events disclose some of the major difficulties and contradictions of the present CFM. As one may have guessed, the institutionalization of a presumed authentic Malagasy value of consent and solidarity, in itself a historical and cultural novum, does not lead automatically to conflict solution and the pacification of political crises. The moral and political authority for doing so at the highest level of the state are very different from the usually local context of ‘making Malagasy solidarity’ (*fampihavánana Malagasy*) and would need further innovations. For the moment at least, the CFM appears to be a unique institution with a very disparate mission: to valorize lost Malagasy values against the threat of modernity, and to connect Madagascar to international accepted peace processes. The urgent quest for solidarity and reconciliation in Madagascar, one might anticipate, is thus not over.

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